

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351854514>

Blended Learning Pedagogy for Inclusive Classroom Design in Nigerian Primary Schools 25-May-2021 15-06-00

Article · May 2021

CITATION

1

READS

11

2 authors:

Delight Omoji Idika

University of Calabar, Calabar Nigeria

63 PUBLICATIONS 46 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Evelyn Ijeoma Orji

University of Calabar

42 PUBLICATIONS 8 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Classroom management practices of lecturers and students' output in post-Covid-19 in a Tertiary Institution in Cross River, Nigerias [View project](#)

Training Young Researchers in Study habits and research skills: Panacea for Examination Malpractice and Plagiarism [View project](#)

No. 20

JOURNAL OF EVALUATION

VOLUME 2 NO 1 JULY, 2017

BLENDING LEARNING PEDAGOGY FOR INCLUSIVE CLASSROOM DESIGN IN NIGERIAN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

IDIKA, DELIGHT O.

Department of Educational Foundations
University of Calabar
Calabar - Nigeria
delightoidika@yahoo.com

&

ORJI, EVELYN IJEOMA

Department of Educational Foundations
University of Calabar
Calabar - Nigeria

Abstract

Inclusive classroom is a major interest of many nations of the world that has been advocated for global best practices in schools. Schools are agents for developing ability, skills, knowledge and sound moral of children and youths for the desired national and socio-cultural development of the nation. Effective learning pedagogy has been advocated globally to enhance potential learners with different needs, ability and culture. This paper views blended learning pedagogy as a facilitating strategy that needs urgent consideration for our inclusive classroom design. More so, the strategy has an inherent capacity to improve active and creative teacher - student participation for desired potential realization. Hence, the paper discussed the construct of blended learning and the utilization, including pedagogical designs, curriculum designs, environmental designs and evaluation designs. Suggestion was made that teachers should embrace blended learning strategy for realistic inclusive classrooms.

Keywords: Blended learning pedagogy, inclusive classroom designs, primary schools.

Introduction

In recent time, there have been serious agitations from education stakeholders for learners of different abilities to be able to access primary education in a common educational setting. This quest came particularly as a result of the perceived stigmatization that trailed special education classroom designs in some states. The quest with its challenges has implications for teacher education, pedagogical design, curriculum design, environmental design and evaluation design. In like vein, facilitators of learning ought to be fully aware of their pedagogical shortcomings and the task required to cause learners of different abilities to acquire and develop desired skills and knowledge.

At this point, it will be expedient to note the very essence of primary school education in Nigeria. First, primary school education is offered for free in many nations including Nigeria. By this knowledge, the importance attached to primary school education is great and the financial expenditure, though enormous, government continues to pay the price for its citizenry. Hence every child whether challenged or not is mandated to access it in all communities. The teaching and learning experience in the primary school is to ensure that children between the ages of 5 years to 12 years obtain a minimum education that equips them with writing ability, reading ability and mathematical reasoning ability. Armed with these abilities, the successful child would be able to function at a certain degree of fulfillment in his or her world. Therefore, whether a primary school learner desires to go for further education or to learn trade, he or she has been prepared for it. Hence, primary school education in Nigeria should afford one desired minimum learning. Through learning, one gains knowledge, skill, ability, growth and development (Anyago, 2010).

Then blended learning pedagogy for inclusive classroom design in Nigerian primary schools is strongly being supported, thus, this position informed the present discourse. This paper discussed the construct of blended learning and utilization, pedagogical designs, curriculum designs, environmental design and evaluation design.

The Construct of Blended Learning Pedagogy and Utilization

Learners of different abilities are accommodated in an inclusive classroom design. This design is the everyday classroom we find in most primary schools across the nation. It is a general education classroom in which pupils with and without challenges learn together. It is the opposite of a special education classroom, where learners are all with disabilities of one kind or the other. (That is, for example, a classroom consisting of learners with learning impairment with other learners with same disabilities and so on). Therefore, if learners are to perform well in an inclusive classroom considering their background differences, learner characteristics and cognitive abilities, then the teacher or instructor ought to be specially thoughtful and creative in balancing various teaching styles and methods in order to meet individual needs for learning and good performance. This is more so, as educators are particularly interested in performance outcome at the end of teaching and learning experience. Since learning entails information processing of attended materials (stimuli) that impinge on one's sensory receptors, an effective pedagogy is apt to cause learning to take place among learners (pupils) of different abilities and different learning styles. Therefore, with an effective teacher or instructor to guide instruction, learners can take active participation in their own learning as they are learning together. Over time, in a well-managed inclusive classroom, effective learning ought to occur.

Considering the foregoing, the use of blended learning pedagogy by teachers in the primary school inclusive classrooms becomes expedient. An effective teacher

or instructor would have to ask for answers to these pertinent questions as a foundation for success in bringing about the desired optimal learning in the pupils.

- What levels of pupils are in my class?
- How can I meet the needs of all the pupils (regular and challenged) in my class?
- Are their needs ought to be met at the same time for each pupil?
- What evaluation format would be most appropriate?
- During and at the end of instruction and learning, will all my pupils be fully engaged and happy?

The answers to these questions are certainly going to determine the level of lesson preparedness and delivery. However, blended learning pedagogy is a sure tool to help teachers answer these questions. What is Blended learning pedagogy? In the simplest language, it is the application or incorporation of different teaching strategies to make learning accessible to every pupil in an inclusive classroom. According to British Educational Communications and Technology Agency (BECT, 2005), blended learning is a combination of face-to-face and online delivery, which they believed suits a wider range of learning styles". Higher Education Foundation Communication Experience (HEFCE) (2005) describes blended learning as a combination of established ways of learning and teaching and the opportunities offered by technology in order to improve students' learning and increased flexibility in how, when and where they study.

From the definitions of the construct, it means a teacher's tool box has to be large enough to contain all the established ways (pedagogical strategies) that could help him or her facilitate learning in an inclusive classroom design. It is needful to always remember that pupils in an inclusive classroom are those with ability, disability, different home background, different cognitive abilities and different learning styles. Though difficulties are inherent, an effective teacher would overcome the challenges of trying to impart pupils at the same time in these classrooms.

A typical seminar will involve the teacher presenting the piece of information (i.e., material to be learnt) in such a calculated way that it impinges on all the sensory receptors where the strength of the individual pupil's learning styles lies most. This is to say that the facilitator or teacher would always teach using a combination of cues that promotes pupils' attention or what is to be learnt. These cues include verbal and nonverbal, visual stimuli such as video and pictorial illustrations, audio stimuli such as sound and music and role play/drama. The classroom ought to be powerfully and purposefully simulating to aid information on processing that could bring about learning. The failure in encoding, retention and retrieval will be very minimal. Studies have proved the efficacy of this pedagogy (Idika, Akubuiro & Umobong, 2012). Below are reviews of some of the benefits of Blended learning pedagogy.

Benefits of Blended Learning Pedagogy for Inclusive Classroom Design

Brad (2000) investigated the effectiveness of cooperative teaching method on students' academic performance in computer under cooperative and teacher-

centred (tradition method) learning environments. The findings revealed that students in cooperative learning group exhibited higher level of academic performance. Chen (2002) also conducted an experiment on two vocational senior high classes to observe cooperative learning effect in the classroom. Results indicated that students in cooperative learning group performed better than their colleagues in traditional learning group.

In the same vein, the study carried out by Bukunola and Idowu (2012) on the effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies on academic achievement in basic science has relevance to this research and together, both have high implication for the educational practices in Nigeria. The study revealed that students in the two cooperative learning strategy groups investigated (Learning together and Jigsaw II) had higher immediate and delayed academic achievement mean scores than the students in the conventional lecture group. The study concluded that when friendliness is established, students are motivated to learn and are more confident to ask questions from one another for better understanding of the tasks being learnt. Similarly, Brady and Tsay (2010) reported that students who fully participated in group activities, exhibited collaborative behaviour, provided constructive feedback and cooperated with their group, had a higher likelihood of receiving higher test scores and course grades at the end of the semester. Results from Brady and Tsay's (2010) study, therefore, support the notion that cooperative learning is an active pedagogy that fosters higher academic achievement. From the Newsletter of the School of Education, Training and Technical Assistance Center, Emerson (2013) made the following conclusion on the benefits of blended learning (cooperative) structures in inclusive classrooms:

- More engagement of students' in classroom learning activities
- Students' articulation of their thoughts more freely
- Students receive more confirming and constructive feedback
- Students engage more in questioning techniques and receive additional practical skills
- Have increase opportunities to respond
- Teachers are better able to assess students and group needs and intervene if needed.

Furthermore, Bucalos and Lingo (2005) noted that when structures are in place for the above level of dialogue to occur, the strategy of the blended learning pedagogy (cooperative learning) accelerates the comprehension process of the students.

Using a blended learning pedagogy can therefore, improve the quality of teaching for pupils' understanding and in so doing extend the teacher's horizon:

- Collaborative learning: This ensures learning together and learning from me another. Pupils' interpersonal relationship could be improved and fostered; social skills of communication and academic engagement could be enhanced and students' development in the positive direction.

Individualized learning experience for all pupils (A typical, typical, challenged, or persons with special needs and exceptionally gifted) all with different needs and learning styles are accommodated.

Flexibility and creativity: Each learner is supported to learn happily and in a unique way.

Virtual learning environments: Here electricity is involved to power video and computer learning. In any case, if power is constantly supplied, visual cues are supported.

From the foregoing, it will be necessary to review a few theoretical support for blended learning pedagogy before proceeding to pedagogical design, curriculum design, environmental design and evaluation design and conclusion.

Theoretical support

Collaborative learning approach: This is a situation in which two or more people learn or attempt to learn something together (Dillenboug, 1999). It is based on the model that knowledge can be created within a population (for example, an inclusive classroom design) where members (say pupils) actively interact by sharing experiences. Learners engage in a common task where each member is accountable to each other. (A situation like sporting activities, debates etc.)

Relevance: Pupils could learn in groups of threes, fours or fives depending on the task to be accomplished. Thoughtfully planned collaborative learning could be adventurous for both teachers and pupils. For example, when the task is assigned, the teacher backs off in order to resist the urge to intervene in pupils conversations. The goal is to remove focus on the teacher while promoting learner centeredness. However, the teacher must keep time to ensure the pupils are centered on analogizing, generalizing and bridging their comprehension with others. Following group discussion, the teacher is to evaluate, not judge the pupils' work. Ideas should be presented to the entire class, thus allowing the small group to come together as a whole. It is then that answers can be compared, gaps can be filled and authority is not on the teacher alone (Chiu, 2008).

Pedagogical Design

Blended learning offers the learners opportunity to learn autonomously. That is, attention is more on the pupils' understanding and active participation in the teaching and learning experience hence, the pedagogical design include;

- i. Learner - centeredness: In blended learning, the greater responsibility and control of the learning lies in the hands of the learner. To achieve this, three different approaches could be adopted.
- ii. The process driven approach: Pupils complete small tasks.
- iii. Product oriented approach - Pupils complete a given task to show their understanding of a given experience.
- iv. Product – oriented approach - Pupils are assessed against the objectives to ascertain lesson coverage.

1. Identification of pupil's needs - Needs are dynamic so they change as one progresses in the learning experience so the teacher takes cognizance of them and provide, active participation for everyone.

Curriculum Design

To consider this topic, reference must be made to what the scope of a curriculum looks like. According to Cookey-Gam (1980) cited in Ogwo (1996) four areas which the curriculum should embrace include:

1. The experiences and activities of children while in school.
2. The distinctive philosophical and/or psychological view points of the teachers which are graded according to social needs of children or the society.
3. A group of prescribed course or sequence of subjects required for certification.
4. The source through which the educational objectives and needs of the society, the learner and the subject-matter are achieved.

In his own view, Okafor 1984 cited in Ogwo (1996) includes in the scope of curriculum the following elements:

- (a) An analysis of human needs, particularly the needs of the students and the society-such needs analysis should include the abilities, attitudes, habits, forms of knowledge, and appreciations which are required for effective execution of special tasks;
- (b) Judicious selection from the vast array of content possibilities, of those content elements that will lend themselves more readily toward the meeting of the needs that have been identified;
- (c) Judicious selection of the learning experiences which are best suited for the attainment of objectives;
- (d) Proper organization and arrangement of the content materials and the learning experiences so as to achieve adequate facilitation of learning;
- (e) Adequate provision for measurement of learning so as to sensitize both the teacher and the student to the effectiveness of the teaching-learning situation; hence
- (f) A general reference to the method of implementation.

Therefore, blended learning pedagogy which is a combination of teaching strategies already exists in the curriculum offering for teaching many subjects. What we advocate is that teachers must be made aware to cash into the opportunity the blended learning pedagogy offers for optimal learning in the inclusive classroom.

Classroom Environment Design

Physical space arrangement and psychological tone.

While primary school system continues to run the traditional education classroom/inclusive classroom design, it is also necessary that curriculum implementers (teachers) pay close attention to the convenience of the classroom.

Physical space of the classroom strongly supports inclusive learning. It should be noted, though regrettably that many public primary school classrooms cannot in the real sense foster any form of teaching because its environment is demotivating and threatening for both teachers and pupils. Cases of collapsing roofs, broken floors and dilapidated infrastructure are common sights in these public primary schools. Government really needs to provide the enabling environment and infrastructure for optimal learning. Blended learning pedagogy can only be effective in an inclusive classroom environment design that is malleable. In other words, the physical space of the classroom environment could be rearranged and arranged as frequent as needed in different forms to accommodate the various needs of the pupils. The thoughtful and creative teacher displays his or her competences in setting it right.

Below are several suggestions teachers could use to facilitate inclusion in a classroom by appropriately manipulating the physical environment (Manno, 2015).

Place Pupils Desks in Group

Put desks in small groups of (2-4 desks per group) so that all pupils have the opportunity for cooperative learning, collaboration and discussion. The teacher's desk could be placed on the periphery of the classroom. Teachers in an inclusive class are up and doing, meeting the needs of the learners.

Provide Centers in the classroom

Attractive centers consisting of various instructional materials such as: abacus, counting chambers, play dough and building block, etc, are provided to aid children learning.

Meeting Spot

Like the school hall where everyone assembles for devotion or meeting, the classroom should be large enough such that a spot can be created in one corner, where all the pupils can come together to have discussions, develop social skills, and participate in large group activities.

Classroom decoration

An inclusive classroom needs to be decorated in a way that does not create distraction and sensory overload. Rather, décor should target needs of the pupils sparingly.

Classroom Safety measures

Adequate space around every pupil must be ensured in the arrangement of the physical space. Injurious items must be kept away. Furnitures and learning materials must be safely kept in their positions. Also direction, arrows must indicate entry and exit ways in case of emergency so that pupils can help themselves. During teaching and learning interaction, teachers must be able to walk to pupils' desks without obstructions.

Psychological Tone of the Classroom

The psychological tone of the classroom is as important as the physical arrangement. The setting should be both productive and conducive to learning. According to Lunderbery, Enmett, Oslanf and Linquist cited in Bucholz & Sheffler (2009), involves creating a warm friendly environment through these procedures.

1. Create a special tradition unique to your class: it would be fulfilling to hear pupils from one class saying to another from another clan "this is what we do in our class". "This is how we agreed to do it". It shows a classroom that fosters belongingness and cooperation. Special tradition in the class helps to grow positive feelings and strengthens healthy bond between and among peers. An example of tradition is beginning the day with a good wish and ending a day with a favorite song that hands are held while singing and things like that.
2. Regular classroom meeting: This helps to build trust. Everybody's problem is everybody's business. It can encourage pupils to work together to solve problems while practising pro-social skills, pupils care for one another, empathy is developed. There is a lot of benefit by the teacher and pupils. Happy teacher-happy pupils, etc. Three kinds of meetings have been identified by Lunderberg, Enmett, Oslanf & Linguist (1997) cited in Bucholz & Sheffler (2009). There are:
 - I. Open-ended meeting where the topic of discussion can be anything of interest to the group.
 - ii. Problem solving meeting, where all class members work together to solve a problem of concern to the class.
 - iii. The purpose for an educational diagnostic meeting, where the pupils' background knowledge about a topic to be introduced is evaluated. The teacher is able to plan his or her lesson for effective delivery.
 - iv. Teach and model communication skills.
 - v. Teach and model reflective or active listening skills.
 - vi. Teach and model self-advocacy and self-determination skills.

Since it is an inclusive classroom, these social skills help to grow and foster healthy interpersonal relationship, order and respect for one another. All these enhance learning for everyone.

Common themes and rules in every class include the following:

According to Manno (2015), the teacher is expected to set clear expectations in form of rules and regulations or dos and don'ts) in which every pupil participates in making.

- (1) Respect for each other's opinions: When somebody starts to talk, everybody else listens. Nobody will laugh or ridicule anybody's answer whether it is right or wrong.

- (2) Group work rules: The layout of the room needs to be pre-arranged so it is conducive for paired work and small group discussions.
- (3) Submission of work and assignments: Provides clear and repeated instructions on expected pupils' work and assignments. Part of the whiteboard or walls in the classroom will contain the deadlines, instructions and rubrics for each work, project or assignment. A percentage equivalent on their term's grade is also provided so the students know how much weight each project, class work or assignment carries.
- (4) Individual and group work grades: Based on pre-discussed rubrics, each project or assignment is clearly defined as either individual or group work.
- (5) Tardy and absences: This will usually follow the school's guidelines on tardiness and absences. Consideration for excused tardy and absence will be given for late work.
- (6) Seating arrangements: This is usually designed such that the different levels of learners are able to support one another.
- (7) Consequences of misbehavior: This is also pre-discussed, when students are fully aware of consequences, they usually stop misbehaving after a warning Manno (2015),

Evaluation Design

Blended learning pedagogy is all embracing. Therefore, evaluation which purpose is to assess the worth of the activity of teaching/learning; to test whether teaching has actually taken place in the pupils, ought to be holistic as well. Therefore, the teacher uses formative and summative evaluation techniques to assess pupils' learning in the various domains of learning: cognitive, affective and psychomotor such that all learning styles are accommodated.

In the course of instruction, the teacher must ensure that pupils learn well by taking cognizance of how information is being processed by the learners. Emphasis must be on the core objectives of the experiences, hence, evaluation should target the objective as well (Manno 2015).

Conclusion

The agitation from education stockholders for learners of different abilities to be able to access primary education in a common educational setting call for an effective and holistic pedagogy that could afford all learners in an inclusive classroom design the opportunity to learn optimally, enjoyably and at their space. This paper thus addressed the various aspects of blended learning pedagogy as a

facilitating strategy that needs urgent consideration for all teachers of inclusive classrooms in Nigerian public primary schools.

Suggestions

1. All stakeholders in the primary education system should come together to review the curriculum to include the blended learning strategy.
2. Teacher preparation should incorporate the teaching of the skills for blended learning pedagogy application.
3. Teachers should embrace blended learning pedagogy for a realistic inclusive classroom.

References

- Anyaogu, R. O. (2010). Improvement of learning in schools: problems, prospects and strategies for improvement. *Nigerian Journal of Education Research and Evaluation*, 9 (2), 67-76.
- Brad, H. (2000). An experiment using teacher-centred instruction versus student-centred instruction as a means of teaching *American government to high school seniors*. www.secondaryEnglish.com.
- Brady, M. &Tsay, M. (2010). A case study of cooperative learning and communication pedagogy: Does working in teams make a difference? *Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 10(2): 78-89.
- British Educational Communications and Technology Agency (BECT 2005).
- Bucholz, J. L. &Sheffler, J. L. (2009). Creating a warm and inclusive classroom environment: *Planning for all children to feel welcome*. *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education*, 2 (4), 1-13.
- Bukunola, B. L. &Idowu, O. D. (2012). Effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies on Nigerian junior secondary school students' academic achievement in basic science. *British Journal of Education, Society & Behavioural Science*, 2(3), 307-325.
- Bucalos, A. L., & Lingo, A. S. (2005). Filling the potholes in the road to inclusion: Successful research-based strategies for intermediate and middle school students with mild disabilities. *TEACHING Exceptional Children Plus*, 1(4).

- Chen, C. S. (2005). Self-regulated learning strategies and achievement in an introduction to introduction to information systems course. *Information Technology, Learning and Performance Journal*, 20(1), 11-25.
- Chiu, M. M. (2008). Effects of argumentation on group micro-creativity. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 33, 383-402.
- Dillenbourg, P. (1999). Collaborative Learning: Cognitive and Computational Approaches. *Advances in Learning and Instruction Series*. New York, NY: Elsevier Science, Inc.
- Emerson, L. M. (2013). Cooperative learning in inclusive classrooms: Students who work together, learn together. *School of Education Training & Technical Assistance*. Newsletter, May/June.
- Higher Education Foundation Communication Experiences (2005).
- Idika, D. O., Akubuiro, I. M., & Umobong M. E. (2012). Blended cooperative/technology interactive strategy with conventional lecture technique and its impacts on student' *learning outcomes in organic chemistry*. *Knowledge Review*, 26 (2), 27-35.
- Manno, M. (2015). Creating inclusive Spaces: *The importance of classroom design in special education posted by quest contributor*, October 26, 2015. Retrieved 30th May, 2016.
- Ogwo, B. A. (1996). *Curriculum Development and Educational Technology*. Makurdi: Onaivi Printing & Publishing.